

Interview Jean Desbiens - Collaboration with Musée de l'Aviation de Montréal
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WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys.

• Presentation of the interviewee :

Jean Desbiens (JD) is a former aeronautical mechanical engineer. He also holds a Masters in metallurgy. JD has been a teacher in metallurgy for professional high schools.

He is currently doing a PhD at the University of Montréal, in the department for contemporary archaeology and archaeometallurgy, with a particular focus on the period around the First and Second World Wars. This is a fairly new field in Canada.

JD's PhD subject covers aeronautical archaeology, from a technical perspective (technical gestures). He has a particular interest for aluminium alloys used in North America during WWII and is currently writing an article on that subject. He looks into identifying aluminium alloys on bombardiers, expecting to find 24S or 17S types, but quite often coming across pure aluminium.

He is one of the volunteers working at the Musée de l'Aviation de Montréal / Montreal Aviation Museum (MAM). <https://www.mam.quebec/>

• The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved ? Defining a recovery project? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing ? What is their approach? Is it similar or different approach if different projects ?

MAM belongs to the category of private museums dedicated to aviation. After the war in Canada, any civilian could buy decommissioned military aircraft, several private companies have been founded for that purpose. These aircrafts were considered as industry surplus.

Most of the existing "wrecks" used to be aircrafts used for training. They are considered wrecks as they have been abandoned but they are generally in relatively good condition because they often stayed in the airports.

There are also many spare parts that have been kept since the end of the war.

MAM has 8 aircraft covering all periods. They often receive wrecks in donations. Underwater wrecks are protected by the government, need to request authorization to recover them.

The MAM currently restores one aircraft that aligns with the Procraft project : a Fairchild Bolingbroke acquired in 1997. This aircraft served as an anti-submarine patrol aircraft during WWII. The team will restore the aircraft to its original state and repaint it in the Coastal Command livery.

- Concept of "conservation": Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle? How do you define long term? What does the idea of "conservation" mean to you for this kind of heritage ? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations ? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution ?

Objective is to reassemble the planes and repaint them to restore their original condition.

In the exhibition, the MAM displays complete aircraft close to their initial functional state as well as other pieces in a more "archaeological" state, such as wing section. Many original parts that have not been retouched. Several engines in original condition.

- Who works on these collections (after recovery) : conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration? Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly ? (addition to Form A)

All the members in the team are volunteers, most of them with a technical background in aeronautics or metallurgical industry. High average age in the team.

No training in conservation.

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact : aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A) ?

Aircrafts are reassembled but there is no intention to try to fly them.

MAM's premises are sheds, old barns. The museum also keep some of the aircrafts outdoors.

The environmental conditions are not controlled, the main wish is to protect aircrafts from weather. No preventive conservation measures.

There is a lot of salt spreading on the roads in the area during the winter, salt migrates into the storage and exhibition spaces. Creates issues with abrasion and corrosion, especially on aircrafts kept outdoors.

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage) : rooms or hall ? awareness about influence of climate on preservation? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A) ?

Uncontrolled environment : the museum's exhibition halls are kept clean and heated but there is no HR & T control.

Generally speaking, the members in the team don't have the knowledge about how environmental conditions can influence the conservation of materials on the aircrafts.

- Reflecting on their own practice : do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about ? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field ? Has your practice evolved through those connections?

The first wish of the volunteers is to save the planes from wreckage and being deboned to recover the metal.

JD points out difficulty in finding contacts on the same topic. He also mentions the volunteers who work in the museum are more or less inclined to sharing their knowledge with others.

JD would like to reintroduce a museal approach, as for the moment the museum is run with an associative spirit, with volunteers from aeronautics and commercial aviation backgrounds.

JD focuses on identifying ancient technical gestures on each side of the Atlantic (riveting, fabric covering), keeping informations about the imperial metric system and knowledge about specific tools. He wishes to arouse the interest of young archaeologists for these topics and aeronautical archeology in general.

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems) ? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks ? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant)? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A)?

The Fairchild Bolingbroke bombardier was given away and has been heavily modified after the war. JD uses the expression "Basic renovation". The current work aims at removing the parts added formerly. There is not much corrosion observed.

3 aircrafts are cannibalized to reassemble 1 complete aircraft. The hand weapons have been replaced by wooden parts made in the museum.

The painting remains to be done.

The team also encounters a lot of issues with synthetic materials such as rubbers.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history ?

Canadian audiences have always been interested in the two World Wars. There's always been a war effort in Canada even if there has been no direct fighting on Canadian soil. There is also an awareness in the public of the influence the war has had on the aeronautical industry.

The subject is brought back to the foreground, with press coverage for example, when veterans pass away.

There is a very great interest for aviation in general, because it has been a means of development of the country for a very long time. Aviation museums are quite popular in general.

These aircrafts have been restored and reassembled; they are presented in the museum in static condition.

Focus on preserving the authentic. Search for spare parts in the scrap box

MAM could serve as a comparative with Europe.

JD wants to reintroduce the museal coast, for the moment associative spirit, people from aeronautics and commercial aviation

WWII twin-engine bomber being reassembled.

Svt ~~receive wrecks in donations.~~

Have room, agricultural area + several barns desaffectedees to shelter

Volunteers who work in the museum, more or less open to sharing their knowledge

JD focuses on the ancient technical gestures of each coast of the Atlantic: rivets, entoiler, e.g. ... + knowledge of the imperial metric system + knowledge of specific tools

Wishes to arouse the interest of young archeologists for more contemporary periods

Aircraft dedicated to Canadians manufactured in France and the UK